

Horizon Europe
SOIL O-LIVE
Data Management Plan

Version 1.0
30 JUNE 2023

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	30.06.2023	▪ Initial version

Action Number: [101091255]

Action Acronym: [SOIL O-LIVE]

Action title: [THE SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES: A HOLISTIC ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF LAND MANAGEMENT ON OLIVE OIL QUALITY AND SAFETY]

Date: [30.06.2023]

DMP version: [Version 1.0]

CONTENTS

1. Data Summary	5
1.1. Introduction and purpose.....	5
1.2. Type of data.....	6
2. FAIR data	10
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	10
2.2. Making data accessible	13
2.3. Making data interoperable	14
2.4. Increase data reuse.....	14
3. Other research outputs	15
4. Allocation of resources	15
5. Data security	16
6. Ethics	16
7. Other issues	17

8. ANNEX I. DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE

9. ANNEX II. Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

1. Data Summary

1.1. Introduction and purpose

This Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to outline how the project's datasets will be managed throughout its duration and after the end of the project. It will cover data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving preservation, and security to ensure proper management principles are followed. This DMP describes how research data was **collected, generated, shared, and preserved** in the project context and after the end of the project, following FAIR data principles. The data generated by the project through the different work packages (WPs) will primarily be utilized to accomplish the objectives outlined in the project proposal. The project will collect data from innovative observations obtained from laboratory and/or field experiments, surveys, and assays specified in the project. Additionally, if needed, existing data from public repositories, digital archives, and databases, such as geographical, climatic, economic, etc., will be incorporated to complement the project's data analysis. The nature of the SOIL O-LIVE data set is diverse in line with its multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach. It comprises **ecological data** (e.g., soil biodiversity, climate, soil physical and chemical properties, land degradation estimates, restoration methodologies, and effectiveness, etc.), **agronomic data** (e.g., olive yield and quality, land management, tree physiological status, etc.), **geographical data** (latitude, longitude, elevation, slope, etc.), **genomic data** (e.g., genetic polymorphisms, genome annotations, genome size, chromosome number, etc.), **chemical data** (e.g., soil pesticide-toxicity data, soil copper concentration, antibiotic, and microplastic pollution). Lastly, it encompasses **socio-economic data** such as surveys on sustainability and market trends related to olive oil consumption and health.

The DMP is a public deliverable of the SOIL O-LIVE project. It includes initial, mid-term, and final reports (D1.3, D1.4, and D1.5). Such deliverables will be available (i) at the internal SOIL O-LIVE repository, which constitutes the internal Consortium document and data repository for the project (Google® Drive Tool); and (ii) at the ARGOS platform¹. In addition, a permanent link to deliverables is available on the SOIL O-LIVE webpages (<https://soilolive.eu>).

The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) and the Soil O-live Consortium have a collaboration agreement. As per this agreement, after the SOIL O-LIVE project ends, they will transfer relevant data, knowledge except, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, and indicators to the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO) and the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC), except for any personal data collected during the project. For this reason, relevant soil data and information will be available also in the ESAC repository (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/resource-type/datasets>).

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the project's objectives?

SOIL O-LIVE will produce various datasets of different types, including both quantitative and qualitative data. The management of this data will aid in achieving the project's scientific goals and disseminating its results. Two main categories of data management are:

- 1) **Research objectives.** The datasets in this category provide all the necessary data for users to reproduce the scientific results of the project. This encompasses experimental data (including standardized analysis methods and agreed protocols), observations, genome annotations, computer simulations, and data production and analysis codes. Likewise, it includes all relevant metadata necessary for EUSO development and validation of indicators for “Soil health” as listed in the implementation plan of the EU-Soil Mission.
- 2) **Outreach, dissemination, and communications data.** This collection includes preprints, technical reports, conference presentations or abstract, educational

¹ An open and collaborative platform developed by [OpenAIRE](https://argos.openaire.eu/home) to facilitate Research Data Management (RDM) activities concerning the implementation of Data Management Plans. <https://argos.openaire.eu/home>.

resources, and data related to outreach, dissemination, and communications. However, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, particularly for the new prototype developed by UCLM, it will be protected by patents, copyrights, or other appropriate means.

1.2. The type of data

What types and formats of data will the project generate or reuse?

The SOIL O-LIVE project will produce different types of data in various formats. Examples of these types of data, as well as their descriptions, are listed in the table below. The sources, formats, and levels of data sharing will be determined based on a survey conducted among the consortium members (see Annex I).

Table 1.

Type of data	Description	Formats ²	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
Geographical (WP1)	Data on the longitude, latitude, elevation, and slope of the 53 orchards selected in the project. It includes metadata with the primary descriptors of the orchards (phytochemical input/hectare/year, orchard size, the density of plantation, age, cultivar type, owner gender, and mode of governance). Land cover and land use data for each orchard is also generated	csv, xml, kml, shp, shx, jpg, pdf, Geotiff	Gathered by the Consortium: In situ collection using a device GPS from the orchard centroid. Gathered by the Consortium: Laboratory validation for polygons and perimeter by using GIS analyses. Digital Elevation Model	Public	UJA	The license used for this dataset: <input type="checkbox"/> CC0 <input type="checkbox"/> PDDL <input type="checkbox"/> CC-BY-4.0 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ODbL <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:	The portion of the data that will be relevant for a publication will be available through the following platform(s) and/or repositories: Zenodo <i>The duration of the preservation will be: N/A</i> <i>Foreseen costs of the preservation: N/A</i> <i>Means to cover preservation costs: N/A</i>
Ecological (WP2-WP3-WP4-WP5-WP6)	Soil Biodiversity: This database contains geo-referenced information about the diversity of soil-living organisms, including bacteria	csv, xml, HTML GeoTIFF, txt Optical microscopy data	Gathered by the Consortium: In situ collection from soil				

² Putative type of formats.

	<p>(symbiotic or not), fungi, nematodes, ants, and plant species. It includes taxonomic, functional, and genomic estimates of biodiversity, beta-diversity estimates for different cultivation methods and comparisons of diversity over time and between regions. Additionally, it provides estimates of gamma diversity variation for each region.</p> <p><u>Soil properties:</u> Geo-referenced data on chemical and physical parameters that it includes all soil components of the EU Statistical Office's Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey (LUCAS)³. Information on two soil horizons, specifically the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm layers, will be provided separately.</p> <p><u>Climate:</u> Geo-referenced data on precipitation, temperature, and aridity at the scale of 1km</p> <p><u>Soil Restoration:</u> Geo-referenced multivariate data on variation in degraded/polluted soils after restoration amendments</p> <p><u>Ecosystem services:</u> Geo-referenced data on pest abundance (<i>Prays oleae</i> and <i>Bactrocera oleae</i>) and fruit</p>	(TAR.GZ)	<p>sampling at study orchards.</p> <p>Metabarcoding and metagenomic data. (BLAST)</p> <p>OTU clustering</p> <p>Functional biodiversity in existing databases (e.g., TRY: Plant Trait database, BacDive)</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>In situ collection from soil sampling at study orchards.</p> <p>WorldClim, Chelsa Climate, CGIAR</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>In situ collection from experimental plots in selected orchards</p> <p>Gathered by the</p>				
--	--	-----------	---	--	--	--	--

³ Orgiazzi, A., Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Jones, A., & Fernández-Ugalde, O. (2018). LUCAS soil, the largest expandable soil dataset for Europe: A review. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 69(1), 140–153.

	damage. Geo-referenced data on soil gas exchange and water flux. Carbon fixation potential		Consortium In situ periodic surveys and experiments				
Pollution⁴ (WP2-WP6)	<p>Pesticides: The data provided is geo-referenced and contains information on the quantity and presence of herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides found in soils and olive oils. It also includes details on the concentration of copper in the soil. Special attention to glyphosate and oxyfluorfen.</p> <p>Microplastic: geo-referenced data on the presence and abundance of soil microplastics.</p> <p>Nitrogen excess: geo-referenced data on soil Nitrogen concentration.</p> <p>Antibiotics: geo-referenced data for the presence of antibiotics and other veterinarian residues in olive orchard soils</p>	<p>csv, xml, GeoTIFF,</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p>	<p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p>				
Agronomical (WP6)	<p>Olive oil production and quality: geo-referenced data on the number of kilograms of oil/ha for each orchard. Data on olive oil quality from standardized procedures provided by the International Olive oil Council based on the physico-chemical profile.</p>	<p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p>	<p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ sample collection of olive and oils</p>				

⁴ Information on two soil horizons, specifically the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm layers, will be provided separately

	<p>Qualitative evaluation of olive oil by organoleptic tasting (IOC criteria)</p> <p><u>Tree-Physiology</u>: geo-referenced evaluation of post-summer drought three health in terms of foliar analyses (C/N) and water use efficiency (WUE) from carbon isotopic signatures.</p> <p><u>Digital twin</u></p>	csv, xml, GeoTiff	<p>International Tasting Panel</p> <p>In situ sample collection of leaves</p> <p>Remote sensing data</p>				
<p>Land degradation (WP3)</p>	<p><u>Soil erosion indicators.</u></p> <p><u>Soil erosion and degradation modelling</u></p>	csv, xml, GeoTiff	<p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>In situ data collection</p> <p>Remote mapping (Copernicus monitoring data and infrastructures)</p> <p>Modelling outcomes</p> <p>Isotopic signatures</p>		Università RomaTre & University of Basel	CC-BY-4.0	All data supporting the findings of the WP3 research activity will be made available in ZENODO and, if applicable, at the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC), the institutional soil data repository of the European Commission Joint Research Centre.
<p>Genomic and genetic (WP5)</p>	<p><u>Plant DNA C-values and chromosome number data</u></p> <p><u>Genome assemblies, gene annotation based on RNAseq, genomic diversity (GBS/ddRAD) data.</u></p>	<p>csv, xml, GeoTiff,</p> <p>jpg (Fluorescence intensity graphs)</p> <p>FASTQ, FASTA, GFF, VCF</p>	<p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>in situ sampling collection and laboratory flow cytometry</p> <p>in situ sampling collection and nucleotide sequencing</p>				

Social Surveys and dissemination & communication (WP7)	<u>Survey data:</u> data from surveys on sustainability practices conducted on farmer populations at regional level. Gender studies in olive farming <u>Dissemination and Communication data:</u> Presentations or abstract in international/national conferences for expert audiences, outreach talks, teaching materials (including scientific papers, talk presentations, videos, and posters)	csv, xml PDF, Keynote, PPT, JPG, mp4	in situ sampling collection Consortium elaboration				
---	--	---	---	--	--	--	--

What is the expected data size that you intend to generate or re-use?

Elevated (Terabyte order) in all the cases because of the extent and the temporal frame of the study and the type of data collected.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility') outside your project?

The EU Green Deal for 2030 and related programs require agriculture production to meet certain standards. This makes the data collection particularly valuable for stakeholders in the olive oil sector, such as producers, cooperative managers, regional and national representatives, politicians with agro-environmental responsibilities, and distribution companies. The data will also benefit olive oil producers from other regions who want to implement sustainable practices in their production. Additionally, the data will aid in cultivating other Mediterranean woody crops, like almonds or pistachio, that grow in similar ecological conditions. Finally, data will be very important for the scientific community in several fields of knowledge because the project will provide quality data to answer unsolved questions on agroecology and the sustainability of agriculture.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

The data will be identified through Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and INSDC⁵ accessions provided by Zenodo repository where data will be stored (see below).

⁵ <https://www.insdc.org>

PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Each data set will have specific metadata standards; examples of metadata are summarized in the table below. Procedures to generate metadata are given in the Annex 2.

Table 2.

Type of data	Metadata format	Elements	License
Biodiversity and Taxonomy	GBIF ⁶	Title, description, creator, contact information, license, dataset ID, geographic coverage, taxonomic coverage, temporal coverage, data quality, data format, data access details, and citation.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Ecological including land degradation	Ecological Metadata Language (EML)	Title, abstract, creator, temporal and spatial coverage, keywords, methods, variables, data quality, publications, data access, and usage.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Pollution	Ecological Metadata Language (EML)	Title, abstract, creator, temporal and spatial coverage, keywords, methods, variables, data quality, publications, data access, and usage.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International CC-BY-NC-4.0 ODbL
Agriculture	AGRIS ⁷	Title, alternative title, creator: personal, corporate and conference, publisher, place of publication, date of publication, subject: classification and thesaurus, description: notes, edition, abstract, identifier, type, format, language relation, availability source coverage: spatial, temporal rights: statement, terms of use citation: title,	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International

⁶ Global Biodiversity Information Facility (<https://www.gbif.org/>).

⁷ <https://www.fao.org/3/ae909e/ae909e00.htm>

		identifier, number, chronology	
Genomic and genetic	Sequence Read Archive (SRA) ⁸ , BioSamples ⁹ , European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) ¹⁰ , European Variation Archive (EVA) ¹¹	Study (title, description, principal investigators, affiliations, and funding sources), Experiment (experimental design, sample attributes, library preparation methods, sequencing platforms used, and any relevant protocols followed), Sample (sample name or ID, organism name, strain, tissue type, disease status, and other relevant annotations). Run: (sequencing platform used, sequencing file format, read length, number of reads, and any associated quality control measures), Data Processing (data processing steps and bioinformatics pipelines applied to the raw sequencing data, alignment, variant calling, quality control), Data Availability, Experimental Factors, Data Quality.	EMBL-EBI will minimise barriers to reuse of data in EMBL-EBI resources by adopting the Creative Commons (CC) license framework across all its data resources in the next 5 years. [2023, https://www.ebi.ac.uk/licencing]
Flow cytometry	MIFlowCyt ¹²	Experimental Overview (experimental design, sample types, and any controls or standards used), Instrument Description (instrument manufacturer, model, configuration, and settings such as laser excitation wavelengths and detection channels), Sample Preparation (sample handling, preparation, and staining protocols, sample source, cell types, labelling reagents, staining procedures, and any treatments or manipulations performed), Data Acquisition (acquisition parameters, settings, gating strategies, compensation matrices, and any data pre-processing steps applied during acquisition). Data Analysis (gating strategies, data transformation, statistical analysis, and any specific algorithms or software used for data processing and visualization. Results,	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International

⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples>

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>

¹¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva>

¹² <http://flowrepository.org/>

		Standardization and Quality Control	
Social surveys	DDI ¹³	Study Description, Documentation (protocols, data collection manuals, codebooks, questionnaires, and any other relevant documents that provide additional information about the study design and data collection procedures), data collection (sample size, data collection mode, data collection timeline, and any training provided to interviewers or survey administrators), data variables, data structure, data quality, data access and use conditions, and publications	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International

2.2. Making data accessible

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The official repository for data and software codes generated by the Soil O-live project will be located on ZENODO, stored in an open file format and with a persistent identifier (DOI) under an open license. Final data, knowledge except, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, and indicators will also be available on the ESAC repository through a direct link from the Soil O-live web pages. Samples, raw reads, assembled transcripts, and genome assemblies will be submitted to BioSamples and the European Nucleotide Archive. VCF files containing variation data mapped to reference sequences will be submitted to the European Variation Archive. In collaboration with Ensembl, the genome data and the mapped variants will be available, together with regularly updated comparative genomics data, in the Ensembl genome browsers. The Soil O-live proposal for collaboration in genomic bioinformatic analyses and the development of open genomic data resources has been explicitly endorsed by EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

If deemed to have potential exploitation value (especially for the novel, cutting-edge prototype built by UCLM), the knowledge generated will be protected by patents, copyright, or other means wherever appropriate.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The data access will be free of restrictions, but respecting at all times the specific licenses of each dataset.

¹³ <https://ddialliance.org/>

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Source code and documentation for data analyses (in languages such as R, Python, etc.) will be available in Zenodo and other specific repositories such as Github, CRAN, etc.

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?

See table 2.

Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Here we provide five ways to improve the quality and interoperability of Soil O-live data:

1. Use standardized data formats (refer to Table 1).
2. Comply with metadata standards (refer to Table 2).
3. Use standardized identifiers, such as DOI for scholarly publications and datasets or ORCID for researcher identification. This enables the unique and persistent identification of resources and individuals.
4. Adopt linked data principles based on Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). This allows for the interconnection and integration of diverse datasets across the web, enabling data discovery, exploration, and aggregation.
5. Open Standards and Open Data: Embracing open standards and open data practices promotes interoperability by removing barriers to data access, encouraging data sharing, and enabling collaboration among different stakeholders.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g., other data from your project)?

Yes, it is absolutely necessary to accomplish the SEM model stated in the proposal. Please refer to Figures 4 and 5 in the GA for more information.

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

The Soil O-live project's methods, procedures, and protocols are available to the public, and they will be accessible through the project's webpage, which will link to permanent repositories (e.g., Zenodo).

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The data will be freely available for the public by using a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, if open dataset-specific licences are respected at all times.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes (explained in Table 2).

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Key data quality assurance processes:

1. Data Collection Process:

- The data collection process at Soil O-live follows reliable and standardized methods, protocols, and guidelines that have undergone evaluation and agreement. Any consortium member can access these standardized protocols and are open for discussion should any issues arise during sampling. Protocols are revised in each semestral in the ordinary consortium meetings.

- The chosen teams of the consortium have the necessary skills to carry out all the proposed samplings and surveys using common protocols. However, training sessions will be provided for certain tasks, such as the ant taxonomy workshops in September 2023. These workshops aim to ensure accurate taxa classification.

2. Data Validation and Cleaning:

- Before any analysis, the person in charge of gathering data, under the supervision of task leaders, thoroughly reviews all data sets to check for errors, inconsistencies, and outliers. The consortium member can access and review their own data anytime to detect inconsistencies or errors. To clean and correct data, we use procedures such as removing duplicates, handling missing values, and resolving discrepancies. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for task 7.1 (*Data communication and interoperability assurance*) and task 7.2 (*Standardization activities*)

3. Data Documentation and Metadata:

- The task leader's responsibilities include validating the dataset, creating and maintaining metadata, and preparing all necessary documentation according to the standards in Table 2. Taskleaders will oversee documentation and metadata quality control, ensuring data integrity through range checks, consistency checks, and logical validations. WP leaders will communicate with task leaders to resolve inconsistencies in case of discrepancies or errors. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for tasks 7.1 (*Data communication and interoperability assurance*) and 7.2 (*Standardization activities*).

4. Regular Audits and Reviews:

- Regular audits or reviews of the data quality assurance procedures will be performed by tasks leaders to monitor and evaluate data quality to identify areas for improvement and maintain data integrity. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for task 7.1 (*Data communication and interoperability assurance*) and task 7.2 (*Standardization activities*)

3. Other research outputs

Other research outputs expected throughout Soil O-live project are:

- Agreed Protocols, guidelines, and procedures will be managed similarly – in line with the FAIR principles – as the data detailed in this document.
- Prototype for the chemical restoration of polluted soils in olive groves.

(Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles).

- 4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Soil O-live will use OpenAIRE's permanent open scholarly communication infrastructure, including storage and archiving (e.g. Zenodo). This implies that data storage and archiving will be free of charge. To ensure security, we will use external hard drives as a backup. We will purchase these devices using funds allocated for small equipment items. Additional virtual space may be acquired if necessary for data backup.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Soil O-live coordinator assisted by the whole consortium members.

How will long-term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept, and for how long).

Data will be stored and preserved permanently in the repositories such as Zenodo.

- 5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

We will perform data backup weekly through two methods: (i) using an external hard drive device and (ii) creating backup copies of data in virtual spaces like Google Drive®. UJA, our coordinator institution, already has free institutional accounts on Google Drive® with several spaces for data archiving (200 Gb each). Each Taskleader will also create additional data backups locally for added security.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes.

- 6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and the ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

N/A

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes.

- **7. Other issues**

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

N/A

ANNEX I. DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE

ANNEX II. Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

ANNEX I. DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE (one sheet for type of data)

Partner:
TYPE OF DATA:
DATA DESCRIPTION:
Relationship to WP and Tasks:
Source (observational, experimental, simulation, pre-existing data, etc.)
Form and format of the data (text, numeric, audio-visual, computer-software codes, instrument-specific, etc.):
Software/Program to read the data:
Size of the data (and estimation of the extension in bytes along the project):
Metadata standard (see Annex II):
Keywords:
Dissemination Level / Data Sharing (public, private, embargo):
Licence for the dataset (CC0, PDDL, CC-BY-4.0, ODbL, Other):
Other research outputs (software, code, protocols, new materials, samples):
Funding for data management:
Data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data):

Ethics aspects:

Other aspects (use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management):

Project 101091255 — SOIL O-LIVE

EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)

REA.B – Green Europe

METADATA CREATION

WP7: Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture. Part 3.

DOCUMENT CHANGE LOG

FECHA	VERSIÓN	RESPONSA BLE	DESCRIPCIÓN	AUTOR	APORTACIÓN
2023/06/21	0.1	FJ Ariza-López		P. Belart Rodríguez	First redaction
2023/06/27	0.2	FJ Ariza-López		P. Belart Rodríguez	Second redaction
	0.3				
	0.4				

Content

DOCUMENT CHANGE LOG	2
1.INTRODUCTION	5
1.1.- IMPORTANCE OF INCORPORATING METADATA IN ECOLOGY AND OTHER SCIENCES.....	5
1.2.-THE OBLIGATION OF INCORPORATING METADATA IN EU-FUNDED PROJECTS. CONSIDERED STANDARDS AND DOCUMENTS	7
2.-OBJECT AND SCOPE	9
3.- DIRECTIVES AND RECOMMENDATIONS TO CONSIDER.....	9
4.- TERMS AND DEFINITIONS	9
5.- BASIC METADATA TO BE INCLUDED IN THE SOIL O-Live PROJECT.....	9
6.- SPECIFIC METADATA FOR DIFFERENT RESEARCH AREAS OF THE SOIL O-Live PROJECT	11
6.1 BASIC METADATA TO BE INCLUDED IN THE ECOLOGY AND OTHER SCIENCES AREA.....	12
EXAMPLE OF METADATA IN AREAS OF ECOLOGY, CHEMISTRY, ETC."	15
6.2. BASIC METADATA TO INCLUDE IN GEOGRAPHIC DATA AREA.....	19
7.- TOOLS FOR CREATING METADATA FILES	19
8.- REFERENCES	20
APPENDIX I. FAIR.....	21
APPENDIX II. GENERAL METADATA SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT	22
APPENDIX III. CREATING METADATA WITH MORPHO. MORPHO GUIDE.....	26
APPENDIX IV. METADATA DOCUMENT.....	57

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Union has clear guidelines regarding the importance of open data and the reuse of information from the public sector (**DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019**). Additionally, the 2020 Program also establishes guidelines for the implementation of FAIR principles (see Annex I) in data management. Aligned with this general framework, the European project: "*The soil biodiversity and functionality of Mediterranean olive groves: a holistic analysis of the influence of land management on olive oil quality and safety*" (SOIL O-LIVE)¹ must develop and implement specific actions to ensure that its data production is consistent with this framework.

The objective of this guide is to provide guidance for metadata development within the framework of the SOIL O-Live Project. Data serves as the objective basis for any research, and metadata plays a fundamental role in the efficient management of data by providing essential information about its origin, quality, content, structure, etc.

In the context of the SOIL O-Live project, it is crucial to have accurate and consistent metadata that enables interoperability and information exchange among the various stakeholders involved. Additionally, these metadata should facilitate the future reuse of the data by other researchers. This guide provides the necessary guidelines for SOIL O-Live project participants to properly document and describe the datasets related to the studies conducted within the project, following recognized European standards and best practices.

Throughout the guide, various aspects related to metadata creation will be addressed, including practical examples and recommendations to facilitate their development.

1.1.- IMPORTANCE OF INCORPORATING METADATA IN ECOLOGY AND OTHER SCIENCES

Researchers in life sciences (zoologists, ecologists, botanists, etc.) are increasingly using data collected by other scientists to address questions at broader spatial, temporal, and thematic scales (e.g., global change, biodiversity, sustainability). In order to do so, research data from third parties must be accessible, allowing for result validation and experiment reproducibility.

If created data is not properly stored and reported, it can be lost. Merely saving tables and results is insufficient because no dataset explains itself, and researchers must therefore include instructions or documentation that enables data interpretation.

¹ Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency (REA), Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-02)

With a classical perspective on scientific production linked to the researcher, Figure 1 illustrates the concept of data degradation in a research project over time. This situation is undesirable and cannot be allowed, especially when the data has been generated with public funding.

Figure 1: Degradation of information associated with data and metadata over time ("information entropy") [Michener et al., 1997]:

In order for data to be useful in the future, it is important to accompany them with metadata.

"Metadata" is information. (Metadata is the documentation that describes the content, context, quality, structure, and accessibility of a dataset.)

The main benefits of incorporating metadata in a scientific research project are:

- They help locate and understand the data to decide the best way to use them.
- They allow for sharing information with others (researchers, institutions, etc.).
- The value of the data will be directly related to the documentation they include.
- Preserving the context in which they were created.

In general, metadata is the information that describes the "who, what, when, where, why, and how" of a dataset. Typically, metadata for observational data focuses on:

- What is the content of the data?
- Who collected the data?
- When were the data collected?
- Where were the data collected?
- How were the data collected?

It is crucial to collect and record metadata at the beginning of the research life cycle and have them complete in each phase of the research to prevent the loss of information that may be necessary in the future.

Assuming that almost all captured ecological data is valuable and should be preserved for the future, the challenge remains to determine which metadata are essential.

Fortunately, the process that scientists usually follow to acquire and use datasets often serves as a guide for determining the necessary metadata. Section 8 presents a minimum content.

1.2.-THE OBLIGATION OF INCORPORATING METADATA IN EU-FUNDED PROJECTS. CONSIDERED STANDARDS AND DOCUMENTS

The following documents, either in their entirety or in part, are essential for the implementation of this document.

1. Agreement signed between the **EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)** and the participants of the SOIL O-Live project
GRANT AGREEMENT. Project 101091255 - SOIL O-Live. EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) (p. 11, Open Science)

This document establishes the following points regarding the management of data generated within the project:

- *Open access to publications in a reliable repository for scientific publications.*
- *Information on any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication will be provided through the repository.*
- *Metadata for deposited publications must be openly available under Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in accordance with the FAIR principles (see Annex I) (particularly machine-actionable), and provide information on at least the following: publication (author(s), title, publication date, place of publication); funding from Horizon Europe or Euratom; grant project name, acronym, and number; license terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. When applicable, metadata should include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the publication.*

2. The SOIL O-Live Project falls within the **Horizon Europe Program** of the European Commission²

² HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions. European Research Executive Agency (REA)

Horizon Europe (HORIZON) is the European Union's Framework Program for research and innovation, designed to promote scientific excellence, technological advancements, and innovation across various fields.

Proper management of research data is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project that generates or reuses research data. It is a key part of the open science requirements of Horizon Europe.

In Horizon Europe, beneficiaries must responsibly manage the digital research data generated in the action ("data") in accordance with the FAIR principles, and they must at least:

- Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) and keep it up to date throughout the project.
- Deposit data in a trusted repository and provide open access to them ("as open as possible, as closed as necessary").
- Provide information (through the same repository) on any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary for data reuse or validation.

Additionally, they must:

Provide open access to research data. This requirement, called the **Open Research Data Pilot**, applies to:

- Data (and metadata) necessary to validate results in scientific publications.
- Other selected and/or raw data (and metadata) specified in the DMP.

Participants of the Open Research Data Pilot must comply with:

1. Deposit the research data necessary to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including associated metadata, in the repository as soon as possible. Other data (e.g., data that cannot be directly attributed to a publication or raw data), including associated metadata, must also be deposited according to the individual judgment of each project, as specified
2. in the data management plan.
3. Take measures to enable third parties to access, extract, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate (free of charge to any user) these research data, e.g., by attaching a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to the deposited data or waiving all interests associated with copyright and database protection using the CC0 tool. The EUDAT B2SHARE tool includes a built-in license assistant that facilitates the selection of an appropriate license for research data.
4. Provide information through the chosen repository about available tools for beneficiaries to validate results, e.g., specialized software or software code, algorithms, and analysis protocols. Whenever possible, these tools or instruments should be provided. (<https://www.openaire.eu/guides>)

2.-OBJECT AND SCOPE

The objective of this guide is to provide applied guidelines for metadata development within the SOIL O-Live project, specifically for the fields of ecology, biology, and other related areas, concerning all data that does not have access restrictions.

3.- DIRECTIVES AND RECOMMENDATIONS TO CONSIDER

- Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast)
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)
- Commission Decision on the reuse of Commission documents (2011/833/EU)
- Commission Communication on better access to scientific information (COM/2012/0401 final)
- Commission Communication on a reinforced European research area partnership for excellence and growth (COM/2012/0392 final)
- Commission Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information (2012/417/EU)

4.- TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

DOI Digital Object Identifier. A code used to permanently and stably identify (usually digital) objects. DOIs provide a standard mechanism for retrieval of metadata about the object, and generally a means to access the data object itself.

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

INTEROPERABILITY The ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort.

METADATA Metadata refers to descriptive information that provides context and details about data. It includes attributes such as title, author, date, format, and other relevant characteristics that help organize, manage, and understand the data.

5.- BASIC METADATA TO BE INCLUDED IN THE SOIL O-Live PROJECT

Taking into account the guidelines of the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission, as well as the *FAIR principles*, the minimum basic information that should be included in the general metadata of the Soil O-Live project are as follows:

1.- DATA IDENTIFICATION: Information regarding the content of the project data that allows for proper identification.

Resource title: Name by which the cited resource is known.

Resource abstract: Brief narrative summary of the content of the resource(s) with coverage, main attributes, data sources, importance of the work, etc.

Resource type: Scope to which metadata applies.

Resource Locator: URL address to locate the data.

Keyword: Tags commonly used for ad-hoc organization of content.

2.- GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION: Information regarding the place where the data was collected.

Bounding Box: Coordinates of the four (West, East, North, South) foremost corners of the dataset.

Coverage: Coordinates of the four (West, East, North, South) foremost corners of the dataset.

Geotags: The exact geographic names/places that are covered by the data.

Coordinate Reference System: CRS (Coordinate Reference System) of the resource

3.-TEMPORAL REFERENCE: Information regarding the data collection time and project duration.

Temporal extent: The time period covered by the content of the resource. Project starting date and project end date. Date of publication.

4.- DATA QUALITY, RELIABILITY, AND REPRODUCIBILITY:

Lineage:

In the context of the project, lineage refers to the trajectory of the data from its origin to its current state. It is a record of the processes and manipulations that have been applied to the data, including the data sources used, the modifications made, and the people or tools involved in each study area and project stage.

Lineage can be documented through records, metadata, process descriptions, flowcharts, or other tools that allow for clear and precise visualization and communication of the data history and applied transformations.

5.- ACCESS AND USAGE LIMITATIONS:

Conditions applying to access and use: Restrictions on the access and use of a resource or metadata.

Limitation of public access: Limitations and other reasons for public access.

6.- RESPONSIBLE ORGANIZATIONS:

Responsible party: Organization associated with the resource. Organization name, contact information (email).

7.- TEMPORAL REFERENCE:

Temporal extent: The time period covered by the content of the resource.

Date of publication.

Taking into account this content framework, an example of the basic metadata for the Soil O-Live project has been developed in Appendix II

6.- SPECIFIC METADATA FOR DIFFERENT RESEARCH AREAS OF THE SOIL O-Live PROJECT

For each of the research areas included in the SOIL O-Live project, it is necessary to create metadata tailored to the specific theme, comprehensive, and accessible.

These metadata are essential for the dissemination, preservation, and impact generation of the results, which is why a high level of involvement is required from the participating researchers.

Researchers are recommended to consider the following guidelines for efficient data management:

- Store the "raw" data in formats that allow for storage, transmission, and sharing of open data.
- Always document the original data and statistics with written reports.
- Document the processes and their results to which the data are subjected.

The participating researchers in the SOIL O-Live project and the data archive administrators have the responsibility to ensure that the metadata are available freely and comprehensively.

6.1 BASIC METADATA TO BE INCLUDED IN THE ECOLOGY AND OTHER SCIENCES AREA

Table 1 presents the minimum set of metadata recommended by CIEEM (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management) for environmental studies.

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Title of the dataset (typically including taxa, data type, date(s) and geographical extent of information) 	
Subject	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A shortlist of key words that describe the dataset 	
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language used in the dataset if not English (Spanish, French, Portuguese) 	
Abstract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A clear and concise statement that enables the reader to understand the content of the dataset Circumstances leading to data collection Explicit aims of the survey(s) yielding the data Brief overview of dataset content 	
Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ownership and copyright of data Contact name and address for further information and support to facilitate access to, and use of, data 	
Survey date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date(s) of data collection (DD/MM/YY) as single date(s) or range Time of day of start / finish and weather conditions (if relevant and not part of methods e.g., birds transect) Frequency of update if survey is ongoing 	

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name of the site(s), and country - Longitudinal and latitudinal bounds of survey extent if sample points are widely scattered - Site description (major habitats and altitudinal range if this information is not part of data set) - Site ownership and access (where possible) 	
Survey personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name(s) of field surveyors and organization(s) - Experience of surveyors in the methods used - Qualifications, professional memberships and licenses held 	
Field methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of methods sufficient to permit repetition and assess adequacy of sampling design - Detailed site map showing location of sample points, transects and/or routes followed during walk surveys - Reference to published manuals and project specific modifications to standard methods - Brief justification of the approach taken 	
Data descriptors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data presentation type (e.g., digital map or spreadsheet) - Definition of the data variables - Units of measurement - Precision of measurements (e.g., to one decimal point) - Spatial resolution (e.g., minimum mappable unit) and for GIS records spatial representation (e.g., vector or grid) - Spatial reference system used in data (e.g., WGS84) - Detailed key to data labels where abbreviations are used in dataset (e.g., in rows and columns of spreadsheet) - Full reference to species identification keys and habitat classifications used - Taxonomic authority cited for scientific binomials 	

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Data processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name(s) of dataset compiler(s) and organization(s) - Date of dataset compilation (DD/MM/YY) - Description of any processing of data after collection (e.g., error correction) and name/version of any software utilized (e.g., GIS package) - Justification for processing decisions 	
Quality assurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Methods used to determine accuracy of observations, and species identification during survey (e.g., re-sampling) - Post-survey assessments of data reliability (e.g., adequacy of sample size) - Conclusions drawn from these QA procedures; including, for example, quantitative estimates of data accuracy. 	
Data archiving and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location of the "raw" data - Name, date and version of computer software with which data have been saved and file type (e.g. .doc,.bmp) - Restrictions on access to the data - Constraints on use of the data - Record of changes to data and metadata with name and organization of editor(s) - Details of reports/publications describing or using the data - Additional sources of information (e.g., publications or websites that describe background to the project or data) 	

Table 1. Set of metadata recommended by (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management (CIEEM). Data source: CIEEM, 2020

EXAMPLE OF METADATA IN AREAS OF ECOLOGY, CHEMISTRY, ETC."

There are numerous examples of studies in the field of sciences that include metadata."

Example:

Soil carbon storage, soil quality and biodiversity data of nine permaculture plots and direct control fields in Central Europe (2019-2021)".

<https://search.dataone.org/view/doi%3A10.5063%2FF1J964VN>

TITLE /DATA SET

DATASET | PUBLISHED 2023 | DOI:10.5063/F1J964VN

Soil carbon storage, soil quality and biodiversity data of nine permaculture plots and direct control fields in Central Europe (2019-2021)

Julius Reiff, Hermann Jungkunst, Ken M Mauser, Sophie Kampel, Sophie Regending, Verena Rösch, Johann G Zaller, and Martin H Entling

Downloads Citations Views Cite this dataset Assessment report

Name	File type	Size	Download All
Metadata: Soil_carbon_storage_soil_quality_and.xml	EML v2.2.0	38 KB	Download
data_soil.csv	text/csv	19 KB	Download
data_bio.csv	text/csv	703 B	Download
data_birds.csv	text/csv	197 B	Download

IDENTIFIER/ABSTRACT

General

Annotations: Data Sensitivity Category: **Non-sensitive data**

Identifier: doi:10.5063/F1J964VN

Abstract: In this study, we examined eight permaculture plots in Germany and one in Luxembourg one time each from 2019 to 2021. These plots represented either entire farms or sections of farms. The permaculture plots were designed and managed according to permaculture principles, with the goal of achieving economic self-sufficiency in production. They also integrated at least two different types of land use, such as grazing and fruit trees. The specific number and types of land use varied among the permaculture plots.

For each location, we collected soil samples from one field representing each permaculture land use type, as well as one control field that reflected the locally predominant agricultural land use. We analyzed the soil samples to assess soil carbon and various nutrients. Additionally, we examined the microbial community structure using phospholipid fatty acids and assessed earthworm abundance. We also measured soil bulk density and depth of humic topsoil.

In terms of biodiversity, we investigated the species richness of vascular plants, earthworms and birds. We also determined if areas were covered by trees or not.

Publication Date: 2023

PEOPLE AND ASSOCIATED PARTIES: DATA SET CREATORS

People and Associated Parties

Data Set Creators	Individual	Julius Reiff
	Organization	University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)
	Address	Fortstraße 7, Landau in der Pfalz, Rhineland-Palatinate 76829 Germany
	Email Address	julius.reiff@rptu.de
	Id	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6152-994X
	Individual	Hermann Jungkunst
	Organization	University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)
	Address	Fortstraße 7, Landau in der Pfalz, Rhineland-Palatinate 76829 Germany
	Email Address	jungkunst@uni-landau.de
	Individual	Ken M. Mauser
	Organization	University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)
	Address	Fortstraße 7, Landau in der Pfalz, Rhineland-Palatinate 76829 Germany
	Email Address	ken.mauser@rptu.de

DATA SET CONTACTS

Data Set Contacts	Individual	Julius Reiff
	Organization	University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)
	Address	Fortstraße 7, Landau in der Pfalz, Rhineland-Palatinate 76839 Germany
	Email Address	julius.reiff@rptu.de
	Id	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6152-994X

GEOGRAPHIC REGION

Geographic Region	
Geographic Description	Germany, Luxembourg
Bounding Coordinates	North 53.76893686673942 degrees
	South 47.68842327777589 degrees
	East 15.416363454268623 degrees
	West 5.726422048086771 degrees

TEMPORAL COVERAGE

Temporal Coverage	
Date Range	<p>Begin 2019</p> <p>End 2021</p>

METHODS & SAMPLING

Methods & Sampling	
Methods	<p>Step 1</p> <p>Description No method step description provided. We will include a citation of the relevant journal article.</p>
Sampling	<p>Sampling Step 1</p> <p>Sampling Area And Frequency In this research, we examined a total of nine permaculture plots in Germany and Luxembourg between 2019 and 2021. These plots were either standalone farms or sections of larger farms. The permaculture plots were required to adhere to permaculture principles in their design and management, achieve economic self-sufficiency in production, and incorporate at least two different types of land use, such as grazing and fruit trees. The number and types of land use varied across the permaculture plots. For each location, we selected one field representing each type of permaculture land use, as well as one control field with the prevailing local agricultural land use.</p> <p>Sampling Description No sampling description provided.</p>

DATA SET

Entity Name: **data_soil.csv**

Download

Data Object Type: text/csv Attribute(s) Info:

Variables

- ✓ location
- farm
- landuse
- plot
- age
- ah_depth
- texture_10
- texture_30
- ph_10
- ph_30
- bulk_10
- bulk_30
- corg_10
- corg_30
- n_10
- n_30
- p2o5_10

Name	location	
Annotations	contains measurements of type study location identifier	
Label	Contains Measurements Of Type	Study Location Identifier
Definition	Attribute location in otherEntity data_soil.csv contains measurements of type study location identifier	Attribute location in otherEntity data_soil.csv contains measurements of type study location identifier
Storage Type	Find more information about this at http://ecoinformatics.org/oboe/oboe-2/oboe-core.owl#containsMeasurementsOfType .	Find more information about this term at http://purl.dataone.org/odo/ECSO_00002767 .
Measurement Type		Q Find more datasets with annotations of study location identifier .
Measurement Domain	Q Find more datasets with annotations of contains measurements of type .	Any text *
Missing Value Code		
Accuracy Report		
Accuracy Assessment		
Coverage		
Methods & Sampling		

- location
- farm
- landuse
- plot
- age
- ah_depth
- texture_10
- texture_30
- ph_10
- ph_30
- bulk_10
- bulk_30
- corg_10
- corg_30
- n_10
- n_30
- p2o5_10
- p2o5_30

Annotations	contains measurements of type soil texture	
Label		
Definition	Soil texture of the 0-10 cm soil profile according to the Association of Agricultural Chemists (AACC) method into seven soil texture classes with decreasing particle size	Soil texture of the 0-10 cm soil profile according to the Association of Agricultural Chemists (AACC) method into seven soil texture classes with decreasing particle size
Storage Type		
Measurement Type	ordinal	
Measurement Domain	Enumerated Domain	
	Code	Definition
	1	S
	2	sIS
	3	IS
	4	sL
	5	LU
	6	tL
	7	T

Can find more examples at the following URLs

- <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/chemical-properties-european-scale-based-lucas-topsoil-data>
- <https://catalogue.ceh.ac.uk/documents/b330d395-68f2-47f1-8d59-3291dc02923b>
- <https://search.dataone.org/view/doi%3A10.5063%2FF1J964VN>
- <https://ecn.ac.uk/data/available-data>

6.2. BASIC METADATA TO INCLUDE IN GEOGRAPHIC DATA AREA

In the field of geospatial data, there is extensive experience in metadata creation and a well-established framework in the European Union through the Inspire Directive and its specific implementation rules for metadata (<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/Technical-Guidelines2/Metadata/6541>). The creation of this type of metadata will be governed entirely by this regulation.

7.- TOOLS FOR CREATING METADATA FILES

There are various tools available for creating metadata for ecological data. In this project, we have selected the open-source software "Morpho," but if someone is familiar with another tool, there is no problem in using it as long as it can be incorporate the previously described items.

Morpho is an application designed for creating metadata in ecology, but it is also suitable for other areas such as chemistry, soil science, etc. The information is stored in the Ecological Metadata Language (EML), and it allows the export of metadata to HTML.

To download this application, please visit: <http://knb.ecoinformatics.org/morphoportal.jsp>

You do not need to register on the KNB network (data repository) because the data repository to be used is ZENODO EU. Therefore, you should store your metadata files locally on your computer and then send them to sig_soilolive@ujaen.es so that we can register them in Zenodo.

Appendix IV includes the basic steps for creating metadata with Morpho.

(The Morpho user guide can be accessed at <https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/software/dist/MorphoUserGuide.pdf>)

In the field of geospatial data, there are numerous FOSS tools available for generating metadata, such as GeoNode, CatMDEdit, GeoNetwork, etc. Any of these options is valid for this project.

8.- REFERENCES

1. European Commission H2020 (2016). Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. Version 3.0. 26 July 2016. [H2020 Online Manual homepage - H2020 Online Manual \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/h2020-online-manual)
2. European Research Council (ERC) (2017). Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020. Version 1.1 21 April 2017
3. Mark D. Wilkinson et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. SCIENTIFIC DATA | 3:160018 | DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18. www.nature.com/scientificdata
4. Metadata Standards. Professional Guidance Series. PGS9 (2020). CIEEM (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management) www.cieem.net
5. Michener, W.K., Brunt, J.W., Helly, J.J., Kirchner, T.B. and Stafford, S.G. (1997), nongeospatial metadata for the ecological sciences. Ecological Applications, 7: 330-342. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(1997\)007\[0330:NMFTE\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1997)007[0330:NMFTE]2.0.CO;2).
6. Riley J. (2017) Understanding Metadata: What is Metadata, and What is it For?: A Primer. NISO. National Information Standards Organization. ISBN: 978-1-937522-72-8. <https://www.niso.org/publications/understanding-metadata-2017>

APPENDIX I. FAIR

It must be met that the data resulting from the investigation is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure that it is managed correctly.

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

(Mark D. Wilkinson et al. 2016)

APPENDIX II. GENERAL METADATA SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT

DATA IDENTIFICATION

Resource title: SOIL O-LIVE

Resource abstract:

After more than fifty years of intensive agriculture application, the environmental situation for many olive groves across the Mediterranean Region is quite dramatic in terms of land degradation, biodiversity impoverishment, functionality loss, which may have already impacted on the quality and safety of olive oil, one of the most important commodities produced in Europe. Through the implementation of a series of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary WPs, this project will perform the first rigorous diagnostic of the environmental situation of olive groves soils at a broad scale, considering the most important areas of olive production at the Mediterranean Region and its relationships to olive oil quality. Soil O-live aims (i) to analyze the impact of pollution and land degradation on soils from olive groves in terms of multi-biodiversity, ecological function at different levels of organization and scales; (ii) to investigate the relationship of soil health status with quality and safety of olive oil; (iii) to implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices that promote manifest soil biodiversity and functionality enhancements in permanent Mediterranean olive orchards across its native range of distribution, that should be translated to improvements in olive oil quality and safety; (iv) to define rigorous ecological thresholds that allow to implement future clear norms and regulations in order to design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive orchards.

More information about the SOIL O-LIVE (methodology and classification) can be found at the [http:// xxxxxxxxxx](http://xxxxxxxxx)

Resource type: Dataset

Resource Locator: [http: /zenodoxxxxx](http://zenodoxxxxx)

Topic of category: HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-02-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency

Keyword: Agricultural engineering, food safety, – Soil conservation, – Soil functions, – Soil pollution

GEOGRAPHIC REFERENCE

Bounding Box:

North: 45,9295

South: 30,3678

East: 27,8118

West: -9,7361

Coverage: Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal, Spain,

Geotags: Olive grove areas in Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal, Spain

Coordinate Reference System:

EPSG4326

Datum: D_WGS_1984

TEMPORAL REFERENCE

Temporal extent:

Project starting date: fixed date: 1 January 2023

Project end date: 31 December 2027

Date of publication: Xx/xx/xxx

QUALITY AND VALIDITY

Lineage:

1. Microdata

The environmental parameters associated with the individual measured points are freely available for download at xxxxxxxx.

Soil results for the 5 countries are available through the JRC land resources management unit under license agreement.

2. Images

Point and landscape photos taken in the four cardinal directions at each point are freely available upon request by email to xxx@xxxxx or via the online order form.

3. Statistical tables

Statistical tables with results are available at xxxxxxxx. Also, there are tables with xxxxxxxx data.

CONSTRAINTS RELATED TO ACCESS AND USE

Conditions applying to access and use³:

SOIL O-LIVE data is free and open to the public

Limitation of public access⁴:

No Limitation

RESPONSIBLE ORGANISATION

Responsible party⁵:

European Research Executive Agency (REA)(1), University of Jaen (UJAEN) (2), etc.....

Responsible party role⁶:

³ Restriction on the access and use of a resource or metadata

⁴ Limitation and other reason for public access

⁵ Organization associated with the resource. Organization name, contact information (email)

⁶ Function performed by the party

(1) Granting authority

(2) Coordinator

Other organizations involved in the project (Beneficiaries):

- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE
- FREIE UNIVERSITAET BERLIN
- UNIVERSIDAD DE CASTILLA - LA MANCHA
- PANEPISTIMIO AIGAIUO
- AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE
- INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS
- UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO
- ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE NORMALIZACION
- ELLINIKO MESOGEIAKO PANEPISTIMIO
- NUTESCA SL
- ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS - DIMITRA
- UNIWERSYTET SLASKI W KATOWICACH
- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO
- CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE
- ECOLE NATIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE MEKNES
- DEOLEO GLOBAL SA

Associated partners: UNIVERSITAT BASEL

APPENDIX III. CREATING METADATA WITH MORPHO. MORPHO GUIDE

Morpho

Morpho is an application to facilitate the creation of metadata and data sets.

Metadata:

The metadata contains information about the content of a data set (its owner, administrator, geographic extent, units, etc.) as well as who has access to the data (the owner, selected users, or the public). The metadata file is stored on your local system and/or on the KNB network. Metadata can be “packaged” with the data set, or can stand alone much like an abstract describing the contents of a paper.

Data packages:

Data packages are the logical units that Morpho creates to represent a collection of metadata and (optionally) data files. At its most basic, a data package consists only of high-level documentation: metadata about a data collection’s title and abstract, keywords, people and organizations, usage rights, research project information, coverage details, methods and sampling, and access information. Once a basic data package has been created, you can add metadata for the individual data tables (row and column information) and optionally include the data tables themselves in the package.

Downloading and Installing Morpho

To download Morpho, go to <http://knb.ecoinformatics.org/morphoportal.jsp> and choose the link corresponding to your platform (Morpho can be used on Windows, Linux, and Mac). You will need to have Java 1.6 or later installed on your system.

Morpho will be installed in one of the following languages (English, French, Spanish and Portuguese), depending on the language in which your operating system is installed

Before you Begin

1.-Create a User Profile

Morpho interacts with the Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity (KNB) Metacat server. But the *Soil O-Live* project will use the **ZENODO data repository**, so you don't need to register and dump the data into KNB.

The metadata and the data package (tables, documents, images) must be saved in your local storage and sent to sig_soilolive@ujaen.es (Zip Format)

Attention: you don't need to register and dump the data into KNB.

On the “Basic Information” screen of the New Profile wizard, enter your profile name and your first and last name.

The identifier prefix will be used to create IDs for metadata documents you create in Morpho, and for data tables or other data files you import using Morpho. For example, specifying the prefix "AJM" will result in document IDs like AJM.1.1, AJM.2.1, etc.

2.-Creating a Data Package

When you create a data package in Morpho, you begin by entering data about the entire data set (e.g., title, abstract, and contact information). This summary information is the *minimum* amount of documentation necessary for creating a data package.

Once the entire data set has been described using the Data Package wizard, you can begin adding information about the data objects them-selves (i.e., information about the individual data tables, such as column names and measurement scales).

3.- Adding Metadata to the Package

The Data Package wizard helps you gather the minimum amount of documentation necessary for creating a data package:

- Title and Abstract
- Keywords
- People and Organizations
- Research Project Information
- Usage Rights
- Coverage Details (geographic, temporal, taxonomic)
- Methods and Sampling
- Access Information
- Summary

Required fields are identified with red labels. You must fill out all re-quired fields before proceeding to the next step. Remember, you can al-ways change the documentation at a later time using items in the **Documentation menu**.

The wizard displays instructions for filling out each screen. We recommend that you read the explanatory text before filling out the wizard forms.

Title and Abstract

The second step of the Data Package Wizard collects a data set title (required) and abstract. The title provides a full description of the package, and should be detailed enough to differentiate the package from

Keywords

Keywords – significant words or phrases that help identify the data set. To add a new set of keywords, click “Add” to open the “Define Keyword Set” screen. Click the “Add” button on the Define Keyword Set screen to add a keyword to the list.

People and Organizations:

There are three types of people to document:

Owner (*required*) The person(s) or organization(s) credited with creating the data (e.g., a principal investigator)

Contact (*required*) The person(s) or organization(s) to contact with questions about use or interpretation of the data. The contact may be the same as the owner.

Associated parties (*optional*) People or organizations functionally associated with the data. For example, the person who maintains the database is an associated party with the role of ‘custodian’.

Research Project Information

Data may be associated with a single, independent investigation, or they may be collected as part of a research program with many sub-projects. If your data is part of a larger research project, indicate this by marking the checkbox. You will be prompted to enter the name of the larger project, its funding source, and one or more associated people or organizations.

Usage Rights

Specify the intended usage rights and restrictions (scientific, technical, ethical) for sharing your data within the public domain. You may request that users inform the contact person if they wish to use the data package, for example, or that they read use and access policies that are posted on a website.

Coverage Details (geographic, temporal, taxonomic)

Coverage can be a single point or a region. After you click the Add button, the Geographic Coverage details screen opens. A textual description of the spatial coverage is required. In addition, you must specify coverage coordinates.

Specify temporal coverage details

Specify taxonomic coverage (optional)

Enter information about the Taxonomic Coverage. By default, you may enter information on Genus and Species. If you would like to enter information at another classification rank or would like to change the default classification rank, click the edit button. Note that the field 'Higher Level Taxa' is dynamically generated from your entries and is not manually editable.

If your information about the taxonomic coverage is extensive (e.g., an extensive list of species), you can import this information. See the Frequently Asked Questions section of the Morpho User Guide to find out how to do this.

Higher Level Taxa	Rank	Name	Rank	Name	Common Name(s)	
	Genus	Gaultheria	Species	procumbens	winterberry	Add
	Genus		Species			Edit
						Delete

Classification System If the list of taxa belong to one or more different classification systems, list the citations for those systems.

Citation Title	Creator	Citation Type	
			Add
			Edit
			Delete

Save for Later Step 12 of 15 Cancel < Back Next > Finish

Enter the Taxonomic Hierarchy (in descending order):

Rank	Name	Common Name(s)
Kingdom		
Phylum		
Class		
Order		
Family	Ericaceae	
Genus	Gaultheria	
Species	procumbens	winterberry

Add
Delete
Move Up
Move Down

OK Cancel

Entering the taxonomic hierarchy (for more than two levels).

Methods and Sampling

Method and sampling information describes the steps followed in implementing an experiment and the experiment's sampling design. Although this information is not required, it helps other users understand your data and how it was assembled. To add a method description, click "Add" to open the Step Information screen).

Enter a method title (optional), description (required), and instrumentation details (optional), then click “OK” to return to the main Methods and Sampling screen.

Study extent information supplements the information already provided in the temporal or spatial extent of the study.

Use the sampling description field to provide details on the sampling design of the study.

Access Information

By setting access information, you control who has access to your data and metadata. For example, you can specify that the public can view your data, or that only specified colleagues can do so.

By default, the settings specified in the wizard apply to all metadata and data tables imported into the package. However, after you have added one or more data tables to the package, you can choose to set different permissions for each table using the “Edit Data Table Access” option in the Data menu.

Summary

Your data package will be created when you click Finish. Please note that you must save the package or the information entered will be lost. Once the data package is created, it is already possible to add tables or other information.

Click Finish to view the data package documentation, or click the "or click to finish this wizard and add a new data table now" link to add a data table to the package immediately.

If you haven't saved your package yet (File > Save), Morpho will prompt you to save the package before closing it. You can choose to save the package locally or on the network. **You must save it locally.**

Saving Incomplete Data Packages

You can save incomplete data packages. Click the "Save for later" button at any step and the incomplete data packet will be saved locally. The incomplete data pack can be opened like any other data pack from the open menu option.

Adding Data to the Data Package

Data documentation describes the data object – the columns and rows, the units used, etc. In this section we will look at how to add data and data documentation to a package using the Data Table wizard.

Opening the Data Table Wizard

The Data Table wizard helps users add data and data documentation to a data package. The wizard steps through the process of importing data (or manually creating it) and adding the proper documentation. Note that you must complete the wizard. If you exit before finishing, you will lose your changes.

Users can choose to import an existing data table and (optionally) extract metadata from it, or to document a data table without including the data set itself in the package.

Fields labeled in red are required, and you cannot proceed to the next step without first specifying the required values

Open a data package and select Create, Import, or Describe the data object

Create

Document and then create a data table from scratch, populating it using Morpho's spreadsheet-style data editor.

If your data table does not yet exist, you may wish to create both the documentation and data table using Morpho.

Import

Import a data table and (optionally) automatically extract documentation from the data table to use in the metadata.

When you choose to import a data file, Morpho will locate the file on your computer, guide you through the documentation process, and include the file as part of the data package. If your data set exists as a delimited text file, you can instruct Morpho to automatically extract certain documentation from the data file (in which case, Morpho will extract table headers and other information contained in the table and prepopulate the corresponding wizard fields with information.

Describe

If you choose to describe your data, the Data Table wizard will step you through the process of providing documentation for it.

Documenting the Data Table

The first few screens of the Data Table wizard collect Data File Information, Data Table Information, and Data Attribute Information.

Data File Information

Once you have selected how you would like to add a data table to the package (by creating, importing, or describing it), the Data Table wizard requests information about the format of the data file.

The instructions in this section are for working with tabular data (for example, simple delimited text).

For more information on working with non-text files or see [Adding other types of data tables](#).

After selecting a data file format, the data table wizard prompts for additional details about that format

If you're importing a data file and don't know which delimiter it uses, open the file and check how the table values are separated. You must also specify whether the attributes are arranged in columns (that is, headers are located at the top of the table) or rows (that is, headers are located on the left side of the table).

Data Table Information

Data packages may contain any number of data tables. In order to clearly identify each, the Data Table wizard prompts you to specify a table name, description, and attribute documentation

A table name is required, as well as at least one attribute definition (we recommend that you document all attributes). The table name is used to identify the table, and should be short but still uniquely identify the table. An attribute is usually a column of the data table, such as date or site. For example, a definition for a site attribute would

clarify what the values mean

Though a table description is not required, we recommend that you briefly describe the table and provide information about the data it contains to document the overall meaning of the table. Click the Add button to open the Define Attribute screen and begin documenting the table attributes

Define Attribute or Column:

Name: Name of the attribute as it appears in the data file

Label: A more readable label for the attribute

Definition: Define the contents of the attribute (or column) precisely, so that a data user could interpret the attribute accurately.
e.g. "spden" is the number of individuals of all macro invertebrate species found in the plot

Storage: Storage type for this field e.g. integer, float

Storage System: The system used to define the storage types e.g. C, Java, Oracle

Category:

Unordered: unordered categories or text (statistically **nominal**) e.g. Male, Female

Ordered: ordered categories (statistically **ordinal**) e.g. Low, High

Relative: values from a scale with equidistant points (statistically **interval**) e.g. 12.2 meters

Absolute: measurement scale with a meaningful zero point (statistically **ratio**) e.g. 273 Kelvin

Date-Time: date or time values from the Gregorian calendar e.g. 2002-10-24

[Help](#)

OK Cancel

Data Attribute Information

Specifying data attribute information helps you and other people using your data interpret the data accurately. For example, if a column of data is titled "spden" – a term that might be familiar to your research team, but not other scientists who may later join it (or view your data on the network) – you can clarify the meaning when you define the table attributes. For each attribute (i.e., column of data), you have an opportunity to document the name as it appears in the data table, a label that may more clearly reflect the value, a definition that further elucidates the meaning of the value, storage information, and category information. Category information, which documents the attribute's measurement scale, is required.

Name, Label, and Definition

The Name, Label, and Definition fields identify the name and contents of the data column. The Name field is required. If you are importing a data table that contains a header row, the value should match the headers used in the data file. Morpho will detect the headers if you chose to extract metadata automatically, otherwise you will have to enter the names manually. If you are creating a data table, the name value will be used to identify the data column. The Label field is optional, but we recommend that you specify a more readable column name if the original name is difficult to interpret. The Definition, which is also required, further clarifies the meaning of the data column. The Definition is probably the most important part of defining the attribute because it provides information that helps future data users understand what the attribute means or represents.

Define Attribute or Column:		
Name:	Q1A	Name of the attribute as it appears in the data file
Label:	Habitat Plan	A more readable label for the attribute
Definition:	Name, Permit Number, County and State of Habitat Conservation Plan	Define the contents of the attribute (or column) precisely, so that a data user could interpret the attribute accurately. e.g.: "spden" is the number of individuals of all macro invertebrate species found in the plot
Storage:		Storage type for this field e.g.: integer, float

Storage and Storage System

The Storage and Storage System fields help identify the structural type of the column values. Though not required, specifying this information helps data users know how your data are stored. Some common types include string, Boolean, integer, float, long, double, matrix, object, scalar, and array.

Category

Categories describe how the data are measured, what measurement scale they use, and how values are enumerated and defined on that scale. Selecting the proper measurement scale is critical because the scale determines the types of statistics you can use to analyze your data. The measurement scale also dictates the type of metadata needed to describe your data set (for example, categorical data never have a "unit" of measurement). When you select a category, the Data Table wizard automatically prompts you to enter only the relevant information. After you have chosen a category, the Data Table wizard prompts you to describe the units, number types, and other details about the categories themselves.

Unordered (nominal) The unordered, or nominal, scale places values into named categories. The different values within a set are unordered. Some examples of unordered scales include gender (Male/Female) and marital status (single/married/divorced). Text fields (e.g., names of study sites or U.S. telephone numbers) should be classified as nominal. When "Unordered" is chosen, the Data Table wizard prompts you to choose whether the values are "enumerated values belonging to a predefined list" (e.g., single/married/divorced), or if they are "text values." Text values can be free-form or can match a pattern that is specified in the wizard as well.

If you choose "Enumerated values," you will be required to define the code used by the values so that users know what each represents (e.g., M="male"; F="female", etc.).

Category	Description
Unordered (nominal)	The unordered, or nominal, scale places values into named categories. The different values within a set are unordered. Some examples of unordered scales include gender (Male/Female) and marital status (single/married/divorced). Text fields should be classified as nominal.
Ordered (ordinal)	The ordered, or ordinal, scale places values in a set order. Ordinal data show a particular value's position relative to other values, such as "low, medium, high, etc." Some examples of ordered scales include level of agreement (Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree), or age class (Juvenile, Sub-adult, Adult).
Relative (interval)	The relative, or interval, scale uses a measurement scale of equal-sized units (e.g., degrees Celsius). The scale starts from an arbitrary point (not a meaningful zero), and so there is no concept of 'zero' of the measured quantity. Consequently, ratios of relative values are not meaningful. Some examples of relative scales include the Celsius temperature scale and the Fahrenheit temperature scale.
Absolute (ratio)	The absolute, or ratio, scale is an interval scale with a meaningful zero point. The ratio scale begins at a true zero point that represents an absolute lack of the quality being measured. Thus, ratios of values are meaningful. Examples of absolute, or ratio, scales include elevation (measured from sea-level), height, and the Kelvin temperature scale.
Date-Time	Examples of date-time values are '2003-05-05', '1999/10/10', and '2001-10-10T14:23:20.3'.

Select "Codes are defined here" as the Location setting to define codes in the wizard.

Select "Codes are imported from another table" under the Location setting to select code definitions from the imported data table (or to import the definition table later).

If the data in the attribute or column are unordered text values, choose "Unordered" from the "Category" list, and choose "Text values (free-form or matching a pattern)" from the drop-down menu next to "Choose". The wizard prompts you to define the text values, and provide the name of their source, if applicable.

Ordered (ordinal) Ordered data show a particular value's position relative to other values, such as "low, medium, high." The ordinal scale does not indicate the distance between each item. Examples of ordered scales include level of agreement (Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly dis-agree), or age class (Adult, Sub-adult, Juvenile).

If the data column contains data measured on an ordered scale, select "Ordered" as the attribute category. The user interface for defining ordered values is the same as the one for defining unordered values.

Relative (interval) Relative (interval) The relative, or interval, scale uses a measurement scale of equal-sized units (e.g., degrees Celsius). The scale starts from an arbitrary point (not a meaningful zero), and so there is no concept of 'zero' of the measured quantity.

You can define a new unit to represent it. To do this, click the "Define New Unit" button and enter a name and description for the unit

Once you have created a unit name and description, specify whether the new unit belongs to an existing unit type, or to a new custom unit type.

Defining a new unit based on one of the existing unit types.

After choosing or defining the unit, specify the precision of the data in the Precision field. For example, if the attribute is measured in meters, a precision of "0.1" would be interpreted as precise to the nearest 1/10th of a meter. You must also choose the number type used by the data: natural, whole, integer, or real. The four number types in the drop-down menu are not discrete classes some overlap. Remember to choose the type that most specifically and accurately describes the data in the attribute or column you are defining. Optionally, you can provide the minimum and maximum values for the data column by clicking the Add button beside the Bounds field at the bottom of the screen.

The four number types used by data attributes.	
Number Type	Description
Natural numbers	Natural numbers are positive and non-zero counting numbers (i.e., non-fractions), such as 1, 2, 3, and so on. They cannot be negative or zero. When thinking of counting numbers, think about counting a basket of oranges, or counting something using your fingers (although natural numbers can be larger than ten). There are no fractions of oranges or fractions of fingers (hopefully!), and there are no negative numbers of oranges or negative numbers of fingers. Natural numbers are one type of whole numbers.
Whole numbers	Whole numbers are just like natural numbers, except zero is included in the set of whole numbers, and therefore whole numbers are positive counting numbers and zero: 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. Just like natural

	numbers, they cannot be fractions or negative. Whole numbers are a type of integer, and they include natural numbers.
Integer numbers	Integers are just like whole numbers, except negative counting numbers are included in this set. Therefore, integers are positive and negative counting numbers and zero, such as -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. Just like whole and natural numbers they cannot be fractions. Integers are a type of rational numbers, and they include whole numbers and natural numbers.
Real numbers	Real numbers are the broadest set of numbers. They can be negative and positive fractions and counting numbers, and can include zero. Therefore, a list of numbers like the following would be a set of real numbers: $-1/2$, -0.25, 3.14, 0, 1, -25, $5/8$, and so on. As you can see from this list of examples, real numbers include integers, whole numbers, and natural numbers.

Category:

- Unordered: unordered categories or text (statistically **nominal**) e.g. Male, Female
- Ordered: ordered categories (statistically **ordinal**) e.g. Low, High
- Relative: values from a scale with equidistant points (statistically **interval**) e.g. 12.2 meters
- Absolute: measurement scale with a meaningful zero point (statistically **ratio**) e.g. 273 Kelvin
- Date-Time: date or time values from the Gregorian calendar e.g. 2002-11-14

Datetime

Format: e.g. YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss, YYYY-MM-DD, hh:mm:ss.sss

Precision: Precision representation:

Bounds: Min. Max.

Buttons: Add, Delete

Annotations:

- Specify the date format using a format string (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD)
- Click Add to specify a lower and upper bound for the date/time data.

Absolute (ratio) Absolute (ratio) The absolute, or ratio, scale is an interval scale with a meaningful zero point.

Date-Time Incorporate the date following the ISO 8601 standard: **year-month-day (YYYY-MM-DD)**

Representation according to ISO 8601	possible values
Year and)	YYYY, four digits
month (M)	MM, from 01 to 12
Day D)	DD, day from 1 to 31

I.e...: 2023-09-14

HOUR

Enter the time following the ISO 8601 standard) hh:mm:ss

Hour (H)	hh, from 00 to 23, 24:00:00 as last minute
----------	--

i.e. : 20:15:00

Completing the Wizard

After you have finished entering a description for each of the attributes, click "Finish" to finish documenting the data table, and then save the data package to save your changes.

New Data Table Wizard

Data Information:

Table (Entity)

Enter some information about the data table contained in your file. If you have more than one data table, additional tables may be added after the completion of this wizard.

Table name: Population sampling data for zooplankton in the Great Lakes, 2000

Enter a paragraph that describes the table or entity, its type, and relevant information about the data that it contains.
[Example: Species abundance data for 1996 at the VCR LTER site]

Description

One or more attributes (columns) must be defined.

Attribute Name	Attribute Definition	Measurement Scale
Date	The day, month, and year that sa...	datetime

Attributes

Buttons: Add, Edit, Delete, Move Up, Move Down

Bottom Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

Callout 1: Click Next after all attributes have been documented to complete the Data Table Wizard.

Callout 2: Each described attribute (i.e., data column) will be listed in the Attribute window. Click Add to add additional attribute documentation or select an attribute and then click the Edit button to edit the documentation.

New Data Table Wizard

Summary

This wizard has now collected all the information that is required to create your new data table.

You can press the "Finish" button to add the data table to your package.

If you want to add more data tables to your package, select the "Create/Import New Data Table..." option from the "Data" menu or [click here to finish this wizard and add a new data table now.](#)

Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

Callout 1: Click the link to complete the data documentation and immediately add a new data table using the Data Table Wizard.

Callout 2: Click Finish to complete the documentation and view the Data Package.

Importing Documentation

If you choose to import a data table, you can simplify the process of entering documentation by choosing to automatically extract it from the table.

If the first row contains column labels, then check the box beside the “Column labels are in starting row” setting.

Note that Morpho automatically places extracted codes in the table under "Code", but you must provide the code definitions. You must also provide column definitions (Morpho does not do this automatically).

Adding Other Data Table Types (E.g., Excel, Mathematica, HTML, or XML)

Stored data, such as Excel, Mathematica, or Word documents, can be added to data packages using the data table wizard.

But note that applications such as Excel and Microsoft Access also allow you to export data as a simple delimited file, which can be imported into

Adding an Excel or other data file to a data package.

Stored data, such as Excel, Mathematica, or Word documents, can be added to data packages using the data table wizard.

But keep in mind that applications like Excel and Microsoft Access also allow you to export data as a simple delimited file, which can be imported into Morpho and viewed.

To add a file to a data pack:

1. Open the data package in which you want to save the data file. From the Data menu at the top of the Data Package screen, select Create/Import New Data Table. The data table wizard opens.
2. In the data table wizard, select "Import" and "Manual", Click the locate button to select the file to import. Click Next.
3. On the Data Table Wizard File Format screen, select "Externally Defined Non-Text or Proprietary Format" and then choose the appropriate format from the list, or "other" if the data format does not appear in the list

Note: It is often preferable to import image files as "other entities"

Once you have identified the data file and its format, use the data table wizard to document it as you would a delimited text file

Adding a non-text or proprietary file to a data package.

NOTE Complex, geospatially indexed images can be included in data packages and described in EML 2.0 and newer versions using the "spatial Raster" or "spatial Vector" entity modules. However, the Morpho do not support adding documentation to these modules.

Adding Other Data Entities (E.g. binary files, images, PDFs)

Data files (scanned PDF field notes, jpeg images) must be imported as "other entities".

To add other data entities to a data package:

Open the data package in which you want to save the data file. From the Data menu at the top of the Data Pack screen, select "Import Other Data."

Select the file to be imported. Click the "locate" button to select the file to import.

Click "Ok". Basic file metadata (file type and file size) will be collected automatically.

Existing Data Tables can have their data replaced while still preserving the original metadata that was so meticulously entered during the initial import. This allows a data table to be described before the data is fully cleaned and finalized, thereby making Morpho useful for active data management.

Editing a Data Package

Once a data package has been created, you can edit its documentation in one of the following ways:

- using the Documentation menu items (for most editing)
- using the Morpho Editor

Either tool permits you to change or delete documentation entered.

Save Data Packages

After creating a data package, use Save to save the package to the local machine.

Exporting Data Packages

To save a data package for use outside Morpho, choose to Export the package. To export a package, follow the steps for synchronizing, except choose Export from the drop-down action menu. You can export to a directory or to a .zip file, which will allow you to easily transport the package. If you choose to export to a directory, you will be prompted to select a directory data (if your data package includes data) will be exported to the specified directory.

EXPORT TO A .ZIP FILE

More information regarding the morpho application can be found at:

<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/software/dist/MorphoUserGuide.pdf>

APPENDIX IV. METADATA DOCUMENT

SOIL O-Live

Title	<i>Guide for Metadata Creation in the SOIL O-Live Project</i>
Creator	<i>UJA</i>
Subject	<i>Data standardization in biology, ecology, agriculture, etc.</i>
Description	<i>Guide for metadata creation</i>
Editor	<i>UJA, Department of Cartographic Engineering, Geodesy, and Photogrammetry</i>
Date	<i>Created: xxx, 2023. Published: xxxx, 2023. Validity: xxxx, 2028..</i>
Resource Type	<i>Text</i>
Format	<i>PFD</i>
Identifier	
Source	<i>Self-created.</i>
Language	<i>EN</i>
Coverage	<i>European, SOIL O-Live Proyect</i>
License	<i>CC BY 4.0</i>
Audience	<i>Researchers and data managers of the SOIL O-Live Project</i>

Project 101091255 — SOIL O-LIVE

EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)

REA.B – Green Europe

B.2 – Farm to fork, Communities Development and Climate Action

WP7

Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

Part C. Open publication of geospatial data

LOG OF CHANGES

DATE	VERSION	RESPONSIBLE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR	Contribution
2023/06/21	0.1	FJ Ariza-López		P. Belart Rodríguez	Ist writing

INDEX

1.INTRODUCTION	5
1.1. IMPORTANCE OF OPEN DATA IN THE INFORMATION AND KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY	6
1.2. THE OBLIGATIONS REGARDING OPEN DATA AND METADATA IN PROJECTS FINANCED BY THE EU. STANDARDS AND DOCUMENTS CONSIDERED	7
2. OBJECT AND SCOPE.....	9
3. RULES FOR CONSULTATION.....	9
4. TERMS AND DEFINITIONS	9
5. ABBREVIATED TERMS.....	10
6. OPEN PUBLICATION OF GEOSPATIAL DATA IN THE SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT.....	10
6.1. LICENSES FOR OPEN GEOSPATIAL DATA SETS.....	10
6.2. FILE FORMATS FOR OPEN GEOSPATIAL DATA SETS.....	11
6.3. REPOSITORY FOR OPEN DATA SETS	14
7. REFERENCES.....	14
ANNEX "FAIR"	16

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Union has clear guidelines regarding the importance of open data and the reuse of information from the public sector (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of June 20, 2019). On the other hand, the 2020 Program also establishes guidelines on the application of the FAIR principles (see annex I) for data management. Aligned with this general framework, the European project: The soil biodiversity and functionality of Mediterranean olive groves: a holistic analysis of the influence of land management on olive oil quality and safety (SOIL O-LIVE) must deploy the particular actions necessary for its data production is consistent with this framework.

The objective of this guide is to provide guidance for the elaboration of geospatial open data in the framework of the SOIL O-Live Project. Data are the objective basis of any investigation and of the current information and knowledge society. For the Opendata (<https://opengovdata.org/>) data shall be considered open if it is made public in a way that complies with the principles below:

- Complete. All public data is made available. Public data is data that is not subject to valid privacy, security or privilege limitations.
- Primary. Data is as collected at the source, with the highest possible level of granularity, not in aggregate or modified forms.
- Timely. Data is made available as quickly as necessary to preserve the value of the data.
- Accessible. Data is available to the widest range of users for the widest range of purposes.
- Machine processable. Data is reasonably structured to allow automated processing.
- Non-discriminatory. Data is available to anyone, with no requirement of registration.
- Non-proprietary. Data is available in a format over which no entity has exclusive control.
- License-free. Data is not subject to any copyright, patent, trademark or trade secret regulation. Reasonable privacy, security and privilege restrictions may be allowed.

Seven additional principles have been added:

- Online & Free. Information is not meaningfully public if it is not available on the Internet at no charge, or at least no more than the marginal cost of reproduction. It should also be findable.
- Permanent. Data should be made available at a stable Internet location indefinitely and in a stable data format for as long as possible.
- Trusted. The Association of Computing Machinery's Recommendation on Open Government (February 2009) stated, "Published content should be digitally signed or include attestation of publication/creation date, authenticity, and integrity." Digital signatures help the public validate the source of the data they find so that they can

trust that the data has not been modified since it was published. Since provenance is for originally-published documents, it is not a reason to prevent the public from modifying government documents.

- A Presumption of Openness. The presumption of openness rests on laws like the Freedom of Information Act, procedures including records management, and tools such as data catalogs.
- Documented. Documentation about the format and meaning of data goes a long way to making the data useful.
- Safe to Open. The Association of Computing Machinery's Recommendation on Open Government (February 2009) stated, "Government bodies publishing data online should always seek to publish using data formats that do not include executable content."
- Designed with Public Input. The public is in the best position to determine what information technologies will be best suited for the applications the public intends to create for itself. Public input is therefore crucial to disseminating information in such a way that it has value.

In the context of the SOIL O-Live project, it is proposed to generate open geospatial data and metadata sets that allow interoperability and the exchange of information between the different actors involved and that, in addition, facilitate the future reuse of these data by others. researchers. This guide provides the participants of the SOIL O-Live project with the necessary guidelines to generate open geospatial data sets within the tasks that have this purpose, following the standards and best practices recognized at a European level.

Throughout the guide, various aspects related to the creation of open data will be addressed, in addition to including practical examples and recommendations to facilitate its preparation.

1.1. IMPORTANCE OF OPEN DATA IN THE INFORMATION AND KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY

In the digital age, technological advances have transformed the research. One of the factors that contribute to scientific and technological development in all research fields is data and, especially, open data. The openness and availability of information obtained from research brings multiple benefits to the scientific community, society and administrations. Research open data fosters collaboration between researchers, speeds up the validation process of results in studies, it helps to carry out more rigorous studies, and allows to maximize public investment in research. Modelling studies (Fell, 2019) suggest

higher returns to R&D if open access permits greater accessibility and efficiency of use of findings.

Researchers in the life sciences (zoologists, ecologists, botanists, etc.) are increasingly using data collected by other scientists to address issues at broader spatial, temporal, and thematic scales (e.g. global change, biodiversity, sustainability). For this, the data from the investigations carried out by third parties must be able to be identified, located, accessible, in a readable format and have the appropriate metadata, so that it is possible to make decisions about them (use them or not), integrate them into their projects and work with them.

If the data created does not have the characteristics of open data, it is very possible that they will not be used in the future or beyond the project in which they were created, thus the experience learned is lost and the investment made will not be as productive. that it could potentially become. In a world with scarce resources and great competition, as publicly funded researchers, we have an obligation that the results of our projects can be reused.

1.2. THE OBLIGATIONS REGARDING OPEN DATA AND METADATA IN PROJECTS FINANCED BY THE EU. STANDARDS AND DOCUMENTS CONSIDERED

The documents listed below are, in whole or in part, indispensable for the application of this document.

1. Agreement signed between the EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) and the participants of the SOIL O-Live project

GRANT AGREEMENT. Project 101091255 — SOIL O-LIVE. EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) (p. 11, Open Science)

This document establishes the following points related to the management of data generated within the framework of the project:

- Open access to publications in a reliable repository for scientific publications
- Information will be provided through the repository on any research results or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.
- Metadata of deposited publications must be open under Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, according to FAIR principles (see annex I) (in particular, machine-processable) and provide information on at least the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, place of publication); funding from Horizon Europe or Euratom; grant project name,

acronym, and number; license terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. Where applicable, metadata should include persistent identifiers for any research results or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the publication's conclusions.

2. The SOIL O-Live Project is part of the Horizon Program of the European Commission. Horizon Europe (HORIZON) is the European Union's Research and Innovation Framework Program and is designed to drive scientific excellence, technological advances and innovation in various fields. Proper management of research data is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project that generates or reuses research data. It is a key part of Horizon Europe's open science requirements. In Horizon Europe, the beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ("data") responsibly, in accordance with the FAIR principles, and must do at least the following:
 - Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) and keep it updated during the course of the project
 - Deposit data in a trusted repository and provide open access to it ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary')
 - Provide information (through the same repository) on any research results or any other tools and instruments necessary to reuse or validate the data

In addition, they must:

Provide open access to research data. This requirement, called the Open Research Data Pilot, applies to:

- The data (and metadata) necessary to validate results in scientific publications.
- Other selected and/or raw data (and metadata) that you specify in the DMP.

Open Research Data Pilot participants must meet:

1. Deposit the research data necessary to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including associated metadata, in the repository as soon as possible. Other data (for example, data that cannot be directly attributed to a publication or raw data), including associated metadata, should also be deposited, i.e., according to the individual judgment of each project, specified in the management plan of data.
2. Take steps to allow third parties to access, extract, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate (free of charge to any user) this research data, for example, by attaching a Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY) to the deposited data, or waiving all interests associated with copyright and protection of the database

using the CC0 tool. The EUDAT B2SHARE tool includes a built-in license wizard that makes it easy to select a suitable license for your research data.

3. Provide information via the chosen repository about the tools available for grantees to validate the results, e.g. specialized software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols. Whenever possible, these tools or instruments should be provided. (<https://www.openaire.eu/guides/>)

2. OBJECT AND SCOPE

The objective of this guide is to provide applied guidelines so that, within the SOIL O-Live project, the publication of geospatial data sets can be considered “open”. This guide is valid for all the topics that the SOIL O-Live project develops (e.g. ecology, biology, etc.), and for all those data sets that do not have access restrictions.

3. RULES FOR CONSULTATION

The following rules apply in this document:

- Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast).
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE).

4. TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

The following terms and definitions apply in this document:

DOI Digital Object Identifier. A code used to permanently and stably identify (usually digital) objects. DOIs provide a standard mechanism for retrieval of metadata about the object, and generally a means to access the data object itself.

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

INTEROPERABILITY The ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort.

5. ABBREVIATED TERMS

The following abbreviated terms are used in this document:

CC Creative commons.

ISO International Organization for Standardization.

6. OPEN PUBLICATION OF GEOSPATIAL DATA IN THE SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT

The publication of open geospatial data in the SOIL O-Live Project follows the general principles of FAIR. The publication of open geospatial data within the SOIL O-Live Project supposes the conjunction of the following:

1. Data set. Data sets created within the SOIL O-Live project that do not have access restrictions (e.g. personal data, confidential data, etc.) These data are created by those responsible for the project's activities following the standards of their areas of competence.
2. Metadata. Metadata is a fundamental part of open data since it provides the appropriate semantics and context to understand the characteristics of the data set (origin, processes, quality, quantities, etc.) that are the basis for decision-making: to use or not that data set, use it under certain conditions, etc. For everything related to metadata, the "Deliverable / .1 Part A "Guide for metadata" should be consulted, which forms an indissoluble pair with this document.
3. License. Application license to the data set and compatible with the FAIR guidelines.
4. Format. Physical data recording format that is not linked to brands or specific payment tools.
5. Repository. Place in which the data is deposited and that through searches allows access to the metadata, data and the download of the data and metadata.

Items 3, 4 and 5 are the scope of this guide, which are presented below.

6.1. LICENSES FOR OPEN GEOSPATIAL DATA SETS

The stipulations governing the SOIL O-Live project contract establish that the publication of the data sets must be carried out "under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a license with equivalent rights, following the principle

'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular".

Figure 1 presents a general outline of what each of the CC licenses allows. Framed with a red border, the licenses to be used are indicated. In this link <https://creativecommons.org/faq/> you can find valuable information to clarify your doubts about the different licenses.

Source: <https://www.wur.nl/en/article/what-are-creative-commons-licenses.htm>

Figure 1. Creative commons licenses overview

6.2. FILE FORMATS FOR OPEN GEOSPATIAL DATA SETS

A key element for a geospatial data sets to be considered open, is the digital format that supports it. In this aspect, the basic idea is the use of formats that are not proprietary, that are well defined by some norm or standard and that are widely used. Below, for different types of data (vector, raster, LiDAR, etc.), the Table X indicates some recommended file formats. Currently, all these formats are supported by the GDAL (<https://gdal.org/>) library, which is widely used among open-source tools, both GIS (e.g. QGIS) and statistical (e.g. R). For the formats that GDAL works with, take a look at: <https://gdal.org/drivers/raster/index.htm> .

Type	Format	Remarks

Vector	
ESRI Shapefile	Developed in the early 1990's, the shapefile format is used to store vector data in either points, lines, or polygons. The main shapefile with extension .shp must be accompanied by at least two other files with extensions .shx and .dbf. Often more than 3 files encompass a single shapefile, all with the same name but different extensions (denoting the different types of information stored in each). This file format requires field names shorter than 11 characters and file sizes less than 2 GB. When sharing these data, it is important to package all accompanying files in zip so they remain together.
GML	GML is an Extensible Markup Language (XML) structure for storing geographic features. Initially released in 2000, the GML format provided a way to standardize geospatial data being shared online. GML files can have the extension of either .gml, or .xml, and as with most XML structures, there is a separate schema file to describe the elements used in the data and the data itself. The GML schema offers metadata for coordinate reference systems, units of measure, and feature descriptors (for primitive objects like points, lines, polygons, and even curves). The schema is also extensible allowing for new feature descriptions of real-world objects like roads, bridges, etc. for use within a specific community. In 2007 GML became an ISO standard, with the official number ISO 19136:2007. GML is the default encoding for all INSPIRE (Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe, https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/about-inspire/563) spatial data themes. Though generally not considered for its ability to support raster data, GML files can also be used to georeference jpg2000 images (https://www.ogc.org/standards/gmljp2)
Keyhole Markup Language (KML)	KML is a derivative of GML used for styling of geographic information, and includes a specific set of features for use in Google Earth and Google Maps. Developed by Keyhole Inc. for use in their Keyhole Earth Viewer, Google acquired the company in 2004 and a year later released Google Earth. Features from the platform were also incorporated into Google Maps. These files are identified by the .kml extensions and a compressed version of KML has a .kmz extension. KML became an OGC standard in 2008 and as part of this standard, a camera view can be used to control what the user sees, add image overlays, captions and icons, differentiating it from other geospatial data standards.
GeoJSON	Leveraging JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), the GeoJSON file format has several defined geospatial datatypes used for easily sharing data online. Compared to XML, JSON files are smaller in size as they rely on key-value pairs instead of a tag-based structure. Recognized by the extension .json and .geojson, GeoJSON files can include vector data with one or more point, line, polygon, multi-point, and multi-line features. All GeoJSON files have the same geographic coordinate reference system (WGS84) simplifying the visualization of these data. Most web maps have libraries to view GeoJSON files, making it a great choice for sharing and visualizing data online.
Raster	
Geotiff	The combination of a Tag Image File Format (TIFF) with geospatial (i.e., location) information produces a GeoTIFF. The extension for these files is either .tif or .tiff, and upon first glance look like standard image files. The inclusion of geospatial information as part of TIFF files can be determined using a GIS or programmatically using GDAL.
Hierarchical Data Format (HDF)	HDF files are very versatile allowing researchers to store images, tables, graphs, and even documents within one file. Identified by files with the extension .hdf, .he5, and .h5, these files are comparable to a folder with a root level containing child folders and files within. These self-describing files can store multi-dimensional data and are useful for storing general-purpose scientific data. HDF5 is the latest version which is much more structured than the previous.
Network Common Data Format (NetCDF)	Developed in 1980 for sharing atmospheric science data, the NetCDF file format has gained popularity across many scientific disciplines. NetCDF files have the file extension .netcdf, .nc, and .nc4. They can be used to store large numeric multi-dimensional datasets with a time-series and spatial component, making them great for computational model outputs. Like the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF), NetCDF files are self-describing ensuring that documentation accompanies the data when shared. A few organizations using NetCDF include NOAA, NASA and USGS.
DEM	
USGS DEM, Canadian CDED (.DEM)	The DEM format are raster-based ASCII files specifically developed by the USGS to capture digital elevation models. They are widely used in the industry because of the high volume of legacy elevation models produced by the USGS. The DEM format is a single file containing 3 record types. Record A stores general characteristics of the DEM such as descriptive name, elevation

	minimum and maximum, extent boundaries and number of B records. Record B contains a header and elevation profile. Record C stores the accuracy of the data and is optional.
Vector&Raster	
GeoPackage	Built upon the open-source database SQLite, GeoPackages provide a platform-independent, self-describing, and compact format that supports both raster tile matrix sets and vector data. These geospatial files have the extension .gpkg and can store many geospatial layers together in one compact file. Beyond sharing data with others, geopackages are useful for field data collection when internet access is intermittent or non-existent as data can be stored locally and later synced to a remote system.
LIDAR	
ASPRS LiDAR Data Exchange Format (.LAS, .LASD, .LAZ)	The LAS file format is a binary file format specifically for the interchange between vendors and customers. Overall, LAS files maintain information specific to LIDAR without the loss of information. LAS files are available for public use, unlike ASCII and other proprietary file formats. The dense networks of coordinate point measurements are so large sometimes that they often need to be split to prevent the file size from becoming too large. When you compress a LAS file, the file format specifically for this is LAZ. You can save significant storage space using the LAZ file format. Like most file compression, LAZ has no information loss. Lastly, LAS Datasets (LASD) reference a set of LAS files. The purpose of LASD is to be able to examine 3D point cloud properties from the referenced LAS files. Through LAS datasets, you can visualize triangulated surfaces and perform statistical analysis.
Point Cloud XYZ	XYZ files don't have specifications for storing point cloud data. The first 3 columns generally represent X, Y and Z coordinates. But there's no standard specification so it may include RGB, intensity values and other LiDAR values. They are in the ASCII point cloud group of file formats which includes TXT, ASC, and PTS. Non-binary files like XYZ are advantageous because they can be opened and edited in a text editor.
GNSS	
GPS eXchange Format (GPX)	GPS Exchange format is an XML schema that describes waypoints, tracks, and routes captured from a GPS receiver. Because GPX is an exchange format, you can openly transfer GPS data from one program to another based on its description properties. The minimum requirement for GPX are latitude and longitude coordinates. In addition, GPX files optionally stores location properties including time, elevation and geoid height as tags.
Data tables	
Comma Separated Values (CSV) and Tab Separated files (TSV)	<i>CSV or TSV files are plain text with columns of data separated by commas (or tabs) and each line represents a new record. Having a field or fields with census tracts, zip codes, or latitude and longitude values allows each record to be spatially aware. These files can be opened in any text editor, spreadsheet software or using programmatic methods. These files can be identified by the extension .csv or .tsv. It is best to include column names in the top line of these files, though it could be omitted (known as head-less files). Beyond a column header, documentation for these files generally remains separate. Efforts like the ICARTT standard (file extension .ict) have reserved a portion in the top of these files to more thoroughly describe each column of data, offering a self-describing option.</i>
SQL Database	
PostGIS + PostgreSQL	Open source PostGIS adds spatial objects to the cross-platform PostgreSQL database. The three features that PostGIS delivers to PostgreSQL DBMS are spatial types, indexes and functions. With support for different geometry types, the PostGIS spatial database allows querying and managing information about locations and mapping. PostGIS can be leveraged in several GIS software packages including QGIS, GRASS, ArcGIS, and MapInfo.
Georef Image	
Image	
Joint Photographic Experts Group JPEG2000 (.JP2)	JPEG 2000 typically have a JP2 file extension. They are a wavelet compression with the latest JPG format giving an option for lossy or lossless compression. JPEG 2000 GIS formats require a world file which gives your raster geolocation. They are an optimal choice for background imagery because of its lossy compression. JPEG 2000 can achieve a compression ratio of 20:1 which is similar to MrSID format.
Based on: https://libguides.colostate.edu/geospatial_file_formats and https://gisgeography.com/gis-formats/	

6.3. REPOSITORY FOR OPEN DATA SETS

Following the steps suggested by Openaire (Which repository to use? In <https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>), in the SOIL O-Live project Zenodo will be used as a repository for all types of data sets generated in the Project. Zenodo is a “catch-all” repository maintained by CERN.

Zenodo is organized in communities. One has been opened for the soil o-live project. Within the communities you can upload resources of a wide variety of types (data sets, presentations, scientific articles, etc.). In a very summarized way, Zenodo offers storage in the cloud, a web application to search for resources and a metadata editor system for the resources that you want to share.

7. REFERENCES

1. European Commission H2020 (2016). Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. Version 3.0. 26 July 2016. [H2020 Online Manual homepage - H2020 Online Manual \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/research/h2020-manual/)
2. European Research Council (ERC) (2017). Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020. Version 1.1 21 April 2017
3. Mark D. Wilkinson et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. SCIENTIFIC DATA | 3:160018 | DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18. www.nature.com/scientificdata
4. Metadata Standards. Professional Guidance Series. PGS9 (2020). CIEEM (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management) www.cieem.net
5. Michener, W.K., Brunt, J.W., Helly, J.J., Kirchner, T.B. and Stafford, S.G. (1997), nongeospatial metadata for the ecological sciences. Ecological Applications, 7: 330-342. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(1997\)007\[0330:NMFTEJ\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1997)007[0330:NMFTEJ]2.0.CO;2).
6. Riley J. (2017) Understanding Metadata: What is Metadata, and What is it For?: A Primer. NISO. National Information Standards Organization. ISBN: 978-1-937522-72-8. <https://www.niso.org/publications/understanding-metadata-2017>

ANNEX “FAIR”

It must be met that the data resulting from the investigation is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure that it is managed correctly.

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

(Mark D. Wilkinson et al. 2016)

SOIL O-Live

Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

Part C. Open publication of geospatial data

Metadata

Title	<i>Deliverable D7.1 – Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture. Part C. Open publication of geospatial data</i>
Creator	UJA
Subject	<i>Data normalization</i>
Description	<i>The objective of this guide is to provide applied guidelines so that, within the SOIL O-Live project, the publication of geospatial data sets can be considered “open”. This guide is valid for all the topics that the SOIL O-Live project develops (e.g. ecology, biology, etc.), and for all those data sets that do not have access restrictions. Indications are offered on the type of license, file formats and repository to use.</i>
Editor	<i>UJA, Cartographic Engineering Department</i>
Date	Created __/__/2023. Published __/__/2023. Validity: __/__/2028.
Resource type	Text
Format	PFD
Identifier	
Source	
Language	EN
Covert	Europe, SOIL O-Live project
License	CC BY 4.0
Audience	Researchers and data managers of the SOIL O-Live Project